

BIAS

Mitigating biases
of AI in the
labour market

Deliverable 1.3

Revised Data Management Plan

Contact us

info@bias-project.eu

www.biasproject.eu

LOBA[®]

CrowdHelix
COLLABORATION. INTELLIGENCE.

farplas

@BIASProjectEU

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Revised Data Management Plan

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Main Author(s)

NAME	ORGANISATION
Mark Kharas	NTNU

Peer Reviews

NAME	ORGANISATION
Marzia Cescon	SVEN
Soumya Kanti Datta	DIGI
Mascha Kurpicz-Briki	BFH
Pinar Øzturk	NTNU
Guðbjörg Linda Rafnsdóttir	HI
Carlotta Rigotti	ULEID
Zeynep Yumrutas	FARPL

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1. Executive Summary

BIAS: Mitigating Diversity Biases of AI in the Labour Market is a 4-year Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Action (RIA). Artificial Intelligence (AI) is increasingly deployed in the labour market to recruit, train, and engage employees or monitor for infractions that can lead to disciplinary proceedings. One type of AI is Natural Language Processing (NLP) based tools that can analyse text to make inferences or decisions. However, NLP-based systems face the implicit biases of the models they are based upon that they learn. Such bias can be already encoded in the data used for machine learning training, which contains the stereotypes of our society, and thus be reflected inside the models and the decision-making.

This can lead to partial decisions that run contrary to the goals of the European Pillar of Social Rights in relation to work and employment and the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals.

Despite a strong desire in Europe to ensure equality in employment, most studies of European labour markets have concluded that there is discrimination across many factors such as gender, nationality, or sexual orientation. Therefore, addressing how AI used in the labour market either contributes to or can help mitigate this discrimination is of great importance. That is the main concern of the BIAS project.

D1.3 is the revised version of the required Data Management Plan that outlines procedures for the storage and sharing of research data. It is delivered during Month 29 (March 2025) of BIAS. It will be formally revised again in M47 (September 2026) of BIAS. However, it will be a living document and revised as needed throughout project implementation.

2. Introduction and overview of work

This deliverable was prepared following internal consultations with consortium members and extensive consultation with the Research Data Office and IT security and legal offices at NTNU for advice regarding formal data processing agreements, security, and privacy concerns.

Additionally, the project has consulted with the SIKT: Norwegian Agency for Shared Services in Education and Research,¹ which regulates the collection of personal data in social science research in Norway. SIKT evaluates the legal basis of collecting data, approves informed consent forms and data storage and security plans. BIAS will do a formal notification of SIKT in advance of any activity that involves the collection of personal data. Some of these reviews are currently underway, and their results cannot be reported on in this deliverable.

2.1 Structure

This Data Management Plan will provide a comprehensive overview of data to be generated, used, or re-used by Work Package. WP1: Project Management and WP7: Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation will neither generate nor use research data and so are not included in the Work Package by Work Package overview. Section 2 provides summary of activities that will generate or use data for ease of reference.

Sections 3–9 are based on the official Horizon Europe Data Management Plan template.² Questions from the template that are relevant for the BIAS DMP are reproduced in *orange, italicized font*.

2.2 WP2: Stakeholder involvement, needs analysis, and co-creation

Survey of worker experiences with AI: A survey for workers on their experiences with AI will be conducted with at least 4,000 responses across all EU countries as well as Iceland, Norway, Switzerland, and Türkiye. The survey is translated into all relevant languages for these countries. The results of these surveys will help inform the design and execution of co-creation activities with workers, HRM employees, and AI developers.

Expert interviews: WP2 includes a series of expert interviews with AI and HRM Experts about their views of AI in HRM. These are semi-structured qualitative interviews where participants both answer a series of questions with pre-defined answers and have the opportunity to share their views in open-ended responses to the questions. The interviews are not recorded, but notes are taken during the interviews and summaries of interviews are prepared for each country.

Co-creation workshops: A series of co-creation workshops in all project countries except Ireland and Portugal will be held engaging workers, union representatives, HRM employees, AI developers, legal experts, philosophers, and other relevant stakeholders to provide input for the development of new bias identifying and bias mitigating software in WP3. This will include generation of lists of words or phrases in their respective languages that can signify bias in an employment context.

2.3 WP3: Technical development of proof-of-concept system

WP3 concerns developing new **bias identification and mitigation modules** utilizing both **Case Based Reasoning (CBR)** and **Natural Language Processing (NLP)**. This development will be based on existing publicly available language models, data provided by project partners Farplas and LOBA, and inputs derived from survey of workers, expert interviews, and co-creation activities in WP2. Insights from ethnographic interviews in

¹ <https://sikt.no/en/home>

² https://www.openaire.eu/images/Guides/HORIZON_EUROPE_Data-Management-Plan-Template.pdf

WP4 will be included in the final iterations of technical development.

2.4 WP4: Ethnographies and SSH mapping of biased AI experiences on gender & diversity

WP4 will consist of a series of in depth, semi-structured **ethnographic interviews** and field observations with employees, HR managers, and AI developers in Iceland, Norway, Italy, the Netherlands, and Türkiye. The results of this will inform final iterations of technical development in WP3 as well as capacity building and awareness raising activities in WP5.

2.5 WP5: Capacity building and raising awareness for AI and HRM community

WP5 will consist of developing a series of **awareness raising** and **capacity building** activities to disseminate the results of the project, the importance of addressing algorithmic bias, and practical tips for doing so. **Awareness raising** activities will be held online and target the general public and are primarily concerned with educating about the realities of algorithmic biases and how they can be combatted. **Capacity building** activities will be day-long courses—primarily physical but also including some online sessions. Three different versions target HRM practitioners, and AI developers, and workers representatives such as trade unions or activists, will give specific advice on how they can recognize and address these challenges in their professional practice. Insights from both activities will be used to create a publicly accessible massive open online course (MOOC).

2.6 WP6: Commercialization and exploitation of technologies

WP6 will consist of developing an exploitation plan including valorization of BIAS results and developing a business plan for a commercially viable product for use in AI-powered online recruitment settings with a pathway towards regulatory approval in order to ensure BIAS has the largest impact possible. This will include a workshop with the standardization body CEN CENELEC on the topic of bias for AI in the workplace, based on the IEEE guidance document and British Standard (BS) 8611:2016 “Robots and Robotic Devices. Guide to the ethical design and application of robots and robotic systems.”

3. Data summary

3.1 Data reuse

Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.

WP2: Stakeholder involvement, needs analysis, and co-creation

WP2 involves a survey of workers on their experiences with AI. The results of these surveys will help inform the design and execution of co-creation activities with workers, HRM employees, and AI developers. We considered reusing survey answers from Eurobarometer surveys, but it was concluded that these surveys were too general to provide meaningful data and have therefore decided to design our own survey as originally intended. The results of these Eurobarometer survey play a supporting role in our framing of the issues in the survey and future work.

WP3: Technical development of proof-of-concept system

WP3 concerns developing new bias identification and mitigation modules utilizing both Case Based Reasoning (CBR) and Natural Language Processing (NLP). We will reuse publicly available word embeddings and data models as detailed in Table 1:

Table 1: Language models used in WP3

NAME	DESCRIPTION
Fasttext word embeddings	Pre-trained static word embeddings available in 157 languages. ³
BERT-based Models	Pre-trained language model (contextualized word embeddings) available in different variants and languages. ⁴

WP4: Ethnographies and SSH mapping of biased AI experiences on gender & diversity

No reuse of existing data was contemplated or will be undertaken.

WP5: Capacity building and raising awareness for AI and HRM community

No reuse of existing data was contemplated or will be undertaken.

WP6: Commercialization and exploitation of technologies

No reuse of existing data was contemplated or will be undertaken.

3.2 Data Type

What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?

WP2: Stakeholder involvement, needs analysis, and co-creation

The following tables specify the types of data currently expected to be generated by the BIAS project. They are identified by individual Dataset numbers (DS). This table will be updated in future revisions of the BIAS project as appropriate when new data generation becomes clearer.

Table 2: WP2 data type

Survey of workers		
Dataset number	Data Type	Data Format
DS 2.1	Survey response	CVS spreadsheet
Expert interviews		
Dataset number	Data Type	Data Format
DS 2.2	Interview responses to pre-defined questions	CVS spreadsheet
DS 2.3	Written summary of interviews by country	Text document
Co-creation activities		
Dataset number	Data Type	Data Format
DS 2.4	Co-creation workshop methodology	Text document, Slide presentations to be used in workshop
DS 2.5	Notes and reports from co-creation workshops	Word document
DS 2.6	Words and phrases that indicate bias	CSV spreadsheet

³ Grave, E., Bojanowski P., Gupta P., . . . Mikolov T. (2018) Learning Word Vectors for 157 Languages.arXiv:1802.06893. <https://ui.adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/2018arXiv180206893G>

⁴ Devlin, J., Chang M.-W., Lee K., Toutanova K. (2018) BERT: Pre-training of Deep Bidirectional Transformers for Language Understanding .arXiv:1810.04805. <https://ui.adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/2018arXiv181004805D>

WP3: Technical development of proof-of-concept system

Table 3: WP3 data types

Hiring data		
Dataset number	Data Type	Data Format
DS 3.1	Farplas application records for CBR research	CSV spreadsheet
DS 3.2	Farplas application records for NLP research	CSV spreadsheet
DS 3.3	Domain knowledge regarding Farplas hiring practices	Text document
DS 3.4	Synthetically generated data for CBR research	CVS spreadsheet
DS 3.5	Anonymously collected, donated cover letters/CVs	CVS spreadsheet
CBR research		
Dataset number	Data Type	Data Format
DS 3.6	Case Base devised from Farplas data	Database

The following presents additional information on many of the hiring datasets, including a detailed data description and anonymization procedures, if any, applied to the data. Farplas will curate two datasets (DS 3.1 and DS 3.2) drawn from job applications Farplas received between 1. January 2020 and 28. November 2022.

DS 3.1 Farplas application records for CBR research

This dataset, described in Table 4, will be manually curated and labeled, consisting of approximately 2 000 application records. Most values already exist as discrete fields in the raw data; those that do not will be manually created by Farplas prior to transfer.

Table 4: Farplas data description for CBR research

DATA DESCRIPTION	TYPE/POSSIBLE VALUES	ANONYMIZATION
Cover letter	Exact cover letter	Any names and address (other than city) manually removed
City of residence	City	Address values manually removed except for city
Gender	M/f/no response/other	None
Age	Exact age (persons under 18 will be excluded)	Birthdate will be transformed into age at time of application
University	Exact name	None
Experience (for each type of task)	(task-id(year of experience); task-id(year of experience).....)	None
Gap in CV	How many years? Is there a justified reason?	None
Relatives working in Farplas	y/n?	None

Worked in Farplas earlier?	y/n?	None
Nationality	Name of country	None
Hired	Yes/no or other information about how far candidates advanced in the process	None
Military Service	Done or postponed	None
Expected Salary		None

DS 3.2 Farplas application records for NLP research

The 2nd Farplas dataset as detailed in Table 5 will consist of up to 70 000 records that will not be hand curated but will be manually anonymized prior to transfer. Other fields will not be included in this dataset **for analysis**, but some information may incidentally be included in the cover letter. This will be supplemented by similar application records from other consortium partners (including LOBA) and potentially non-consortium organizations. Because these data will be structured in the same way and treated the same way for Open Sciences practices—just the company they come from will vary—we do not distinguish them as separate datasets at this time. This may change in future versions of the Data Management Plan depending on the nature of the data from different sources.

Table 5: Farplas data used in NLP research

DATA DESCRIPTION	TYPE/POSSIBLE VALUES	ANONYMIZATION
Age	Exact age (persons under 18 will be excluded)	Birthdate will be transformed into age at time of application
Gender	M/f/no response/other	None
Cover letter	Exact cover letter	Any directly personally identifying information such as names or exact addresses will be manually removed
Nationality	Name of country	None
Hired	Yes/no or other information about how far candidates advanced in the process	None

DS 3.3 Domain knowledge regarding Farplas hiring practices

The AI method used in the project, specifically Case-Based Reasoning (CBR), allows for the integration of domain knowledge in addition to job application data. We have, to a limited extent, captured the domain knowledge of expert recruiters. This knowledge reflects how recruiters utilize applicant data in practice.

For example, "district" is an important attribute because the employer provides bus services to pick up employees from specific areas in Istanbul each morning. If a candidate does not live in one of these areas, they are not shortlisted. Therefore, the system must be aware of these specific areas. Another example involves tacit recruiter knowledge related to job types and university education requirements. For certain jobs, recruiters consider aspects of university education that may not be explicitly stated in the

job requirements. By conducting authentic recruiting sessions and applying knowledge engineering methods, this type of tacit knowledge has been made explicit and incorporated into the system. It is not causal knowledge but rather structural knowledge.

DS 3.4 Synthetically generated data for CBR research

At the start of the project, there were around 70,000 candidate (i.e., job applicant) records, but this data set did not include any decisions made, i.e., "labels." Farplas recruiters began labelling the data, but since this task is time-consuming, we received only 1,854 labelled records, categorized across six types of positions, by September 2024. However, this labelled data set didn't contain a sufficient number of good candidates that had been shortlisted by recruiters. Recognizing that we would never obtain enough labelled data with a sufficient number of qualified candidates, we decided to create synthetic data by tweaking the original data.

In this process, candidate data, consisting of around 20 attributes (e.g., age, education level, university department, living area, municipality, etc.), was used to create a set of new synthetic data.

We applied a type of mutation to the shortlisted candidates. For this, we created a mutate function that takes a candidate and returns a modified copy with a small change. This results in two candidates who are very similar, except for one—or in some cases, two—attributes, as will be explained shortly.

Mutation operation for each feature type:

- Birth date: add/subtract a few years (e.g. 1-3 years)
- Gender: Flip (the value is binary)
- Nationality: Flip
- District: Switch
- Employment status: Switch
- Overall experience Period: add/subtract a few years
- Education level: add/subtract very few (± 1) levels
- Graduation status: Switch
- High School name / type / department: switch

If the attribute chosen for mutation had a dependency on another attribute, both values were adjusted to avoid any inconsistencies. For example, a candidate living in "Persaunet" would have "Trondheim" as their municipality. The newly generated data can be considered counterfactual. In this way, the new data set remained "loyal" to the original data while including both candidates who matched the job requirements and those who did not.

The data creation process may be iterative. If the newly generated data does not meet the goal of producing more "good application data," we will adjust the method and create additional data. Currently, we are in the testing phase, assessing whether a sufficient percentage of "good candidates" has been achieved.

DS 3.5 Anonymously collected, donated cover letters/CVs

BIAS will also solicit donation of cover letters from members of the general public to supplement DS 3.2. These will be collected by partner BFH and NTNU through anonymous online data donation portal. The donated records will include:

Table 6 Anonymously collected, donated cover letters/CVs

DATA DESCRIPTION	TYPE/POSSIBLE VALUES	ANONYMIZATION (to be completed by volunteer prior to donation)
Gender	M/f/non-binary/no response/other (with free text field)	None
Cover letter	Exact cover letter	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Any names—the applicant’s name or the names of any other individuals mentioned The name of any institution or organization, e.g. current or previous employer, university, club or society Any location if it could be used to directly identify an organization (e.g. “I work at the largest software company in Norway” should be changed either to remove Norway edited to read “I work at a large software company in Norway”) If possible, replace any deleted text with: “[redacted]”
Nationality	Name of country	None
Age (when application submitted)	Age range: 18-25, 26-35, 36-45, 46-55, 56+	None
Interviewed for job?	Yes/no/no answer	None
Hired	Yes/no/no answer	None
Field of job applied for	Free text	None

WP4: Ethnographies and SSH mapping of biased AI experiences on gender & diversity

Table 7: WP4 data types

Ethnographic interviews		
Dataset number	Data Type	Data Format
DS 4.1	Interview recordings	Sound recordings
DS 4.2	Anonymized verbatim transcripts in original language and English translation	Text document
DS 4.3	Fieldnotes from ethnographic fieldwork	Text document

WP5: Capacity building and raising awareness for AI and HRM community

Table 8: WP5 data types

Awareness raising events		
Dataset number	Data Type	Data Format
DS 5.1	Awareness raising course materials	Text document of

		course outline, Slide presentations, videos
DS 5.2	Awareness raising activities	Text document of notes from sessions, audio/video recording of webinar presentations
Capacity building events		
Dataset number	Data Type	Data Format
DS 5.3	Capacity building course materials	Text document of course outline, slide presentations, videos
DS 5.4	Capacity building activities	Text document of notes from sessions, audio/video recording of presentations
MOOC		
Dataset number	Data Type	Data Format
DS 5.5	MOOC course content	Text document of course notes; Slide presentations and videos integrated into MOOC

WP6: Commercialization and exploitation of technologies

Table 9: WP6 data types

CEN CENELAC workshop		
Dataset number	Data Type	Data Format
DS 6.1	Workshop agreement	Word document
DS 6.2	Workshop results	Word document of notes from workshop

3.3 Purpose of data

What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?

Survey of workers (DS 2.1): Discover a baseline of to what extent workers across Europe have experienced AI in an employment context and what their opinions of such use is. Will inform co-creation activities, technical development, ethnographic interviews, awareness raising, and capacity building efforts.

Expert interviews (DS 2.2, 2.3): Discover a baseline of to what extent experts in the AI and HRM fields across Europe believe AI is used in employment contexts and to gauge their opinions of such use. Combined with worker experiences, will inform co-creation activities, technical development, ethnographic interviews, awareness raising, and capacity building efforts.

Co-creation activities (DS 2.4, 2.5, 2.6): Will provide a more nuanced view of workers and AI developers experiences of AI in employment contexts with a special consideration towards technical development and business validation. Will also inform ethnographic interviews, awareness raising, and capacity building activities. Will also provide specific words and phrases useful in NLP research.

Hiring data (DS 3.1, 3.2, 3.3, 3.4, 3.5): Will be the primary basis for training bias identifying and mitigating NLP and CBR systems. Raw data from applications will be used as training data for NLP research. Curated datasets combined with notes on Farplas hiring procedures will create a case base (DS 3.6) that will be used in CBR research.

Ethnographic interviews (DS 4.1, 4.2, 4.3): Will provide one of the largest qualitative datasets specifically about bias, AI, and employment useful for BIAS researchers and others to advance the fields of Science and Technology Studies, Worker Studies, and related fields. Will also inform technical development, awareness raising, and capacity building activities as well as plans for commercial exploitation.

Awareness raising activities (DS 5.1, 5.2): Will provide content for materials that can educate about algorithmic bias in employment contexts after completion of BIAS project, including the MOOC. Will inform plans for commercial exploitation.

Capacity building activities (DS 5.3, 5.4): Will provide content for materials that can educate about algorithmic bias in employment contexts after completion of BIAS project, including the MOOC. Will inform plans for commercial exploitation.

MOOC (DS 5.5): Will provide a platform for the knowledge of BIAS to be exploited post-project.

CEN CENELAC workshop (DS 6.1, 6.2): Will provide mechanism for BIAS project results to inform future regulation and standardization efforts.

All data will also be used for scientific publications disseminating BIAS project results.

3.4 Data size

What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?

Most data is in the form of Excel spreadsheets, CVS files, or word documents and is expected to be of negligible size. Audio recordings of ethnographic interviews will be deleted once anonymized verbatim transcripts are made. Recordings of some aspects of awareness raising and capacity building activities may be larger, but total data is estimated to be under 1TB.

3.5 Origin and provenance

What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?

Survey of workers (DS 2.1): Responses from survey takers across Europe.

Expert interviews (DS 2.2, 2.3): Notes and interview question responses generated during interviews with identified experts.

Co-creation activities (DS 2.4, 2.5, 2.6): Notes from workshops conducted with interested stakeholders in partner countries.

Farplas hiring data (DS 3.1, 3.2): Application records (both blue and white collar) from job applicants to open Farplas positions in 2021–2022.

Farplas hiring procedures and case base (DS 3.3, 3.6): Small curated dataset of Farplas hiring decisions and conversations with Farplas HR team regarding their hiring procedures.

Synthetic data for CBR (DS 3.4): Created from DS 3.3 as described above in Section 3.2 of this DMP

Anonymously collected, donated cover letters/CVs (DS 3.5): Donated by members of the public following individual anonymization

Fasttext language model: <https://fasttext.cc/> (publicly available)

BERT-based language models: <https://huggingface.co/> (publicly available)

Ethnographic interviews (DS 4.1, 4.2, 4.3): Interviews with volunteer informants and field observations in the indicated countries.

Awareness raising activities (DS 5.1, 5.2): Notes from and content created for online awareness raising events designed to engage everyday citizens.

Capacity building activities (DS 5.3, 5.4): Notes from and content created for physical capacity building events in project partner countries designed to engage HRM employees and AI developers.

MOOC (DS 5.5): Content created during awareness raising and capacity building activities that is deemed to be most useful for disseminating project learning following completing of the project.

CEN CENELAC workshop (DS 6.1, 6.2): Notes generated during and in preparation for workshop.

3.6 Data Utility

To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

In general, raw data may be of interest to other academic researchers and AI developers. Other constituencies may have a vested interest in conclusions drawn from this data, but could conceivably be interested in conducting their own analyses of the data in certain contexts. However, as described below much of the data is internal in nature and this will not be made public in raw form.

Survey of workers (DS 2.1): Other academic researchers, policymakers, HR managers at companies, union leaders, AI developers

Expert interviews (DS 2.2, 2.3): Other academic researchers, policymakers, union leaders, HR experts, AI developers

Co-creation activities (DS 2.4, 2.5, 2.6): Other academic researchers, policymakers, HR managers at companies, union leaders, AI developers, other research projects considering co-creation activities with similar methods or goals.

Farplas and donated hiring data and case base (DS 3.1, 3.2, 3.4, 3.5, 3.6): Other academic researchers and AI developers, especially in NLP and CBR.

Ethnographic interviews (DS 4.1, 4.2, 4.3): Other academic researchers, especially those engaged in work-life studies and STS; AI developers, union representatives, HR managers at companies.

Awareness raising activities (DS 5.1, 5.2): General public interested in issues of AI and employment, other projects planning similar activities

Capacity building activities (DS 5.3, 5.4): AI developers, HR managers at companies, policymakers, other research projects planning similar activities

MOOC (DS 5.5): Anyone who would like to learn results and best practices developed during the project in a structured manner, likely HR managers at companies and AI developers.

CEN CENELAC workshop (DS 6.1, 6.2): Policymakers and standardization bodies, AI developers

4. FAIR data

Much of the content regarding metadata and repositories is preliminary and will be updated in future revisions of the Data Management Plan

4.1 Making data findable including provisions for metadata

Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.

Much of the data outlined above consists of internal reports or summaries of activities which are necessary for carrying out BIAS project activities and which do have research value internal to BIAS but are not useful for other researchers to have direct access to it. We currently have plans to make the results and conclusions from all of these activities public, which will also contain sufficient information on the methodology for researchers to evaluate how the conclusions were generated. These are detailed further in Section 5: Other research outputs.

Some data is sufficiently structured and comprehensive that it would be of use to other researchers and interested parties to perform independent analyses. These include:

- DS 2.1: Survey of workers: Survey responses
- DS 2.2: Expert interviews: Interview responses to pre-defined questions
- DS 2.6: Co-creation workshops: Words and phrases that indicate bias
- DS 3.1: Farplas application records for CBR research
- DS 3.2: Farplas application records for NLP research
- DS 3.4: Synthetically generated data for CBR research
- DS 3.5: Anonymously collected, donated cover letters/CVs
- DS 4.2: Ethnographic interviews: Anonymized verbatim transcripts in original language and English translation

The BIAS project has had initial deliberations concerning data access, and the General Assembly has made decisions, as described in Table 10. These decisions may be revised as appropriate during remaining project implementation, and will be revisited in a final version of this Data Management Plan, due in September 2026.

Table 10: Current access provision plans for BIAS datasets

Dataset number	Access provision plans
DS 2.1	Fully accessible in Zenodo
DS 2.2	Fully accessible in Zenodo
DS 2.6	Fully accessible in GitHub and potentially HuggingFace
DS 3.1	Confidential
DS 3.2	Confidential
DS 3.4	Confidential
DS 3.5	Fully accessible in Zenodo for those who provide consent
DS 4.2	Confidential

At the time of the previous DMP submission, it was not clear whether DS 3.1 and 3.2 will be made available to other researchers or kept confidential because of Farplas' business

interests. Following internal discussions, it was determined that the data should be kept confidential. In addition to business interests, the approval from Sikt to process this data was received on the basis of Public Interest (General Data Protection Regulation art. 6 nr .1 e); individuals did not consent to the processing of their data. This ethical concern also advised keeping the data confidential.

At the time of submission of this version of the DMP, DS3.4 was only recently planned for, thus discussions on access provisions are still ongoing.

The consent form for volunteers to submit their anonymized cover letters and/or CVs in DS3.5 has an option for volunteers to consent to have their data shared beyond the consortium or to have access restricted to the BIAS consortium within the confines of the BIAS project. A dataset consisting of data from volunteers who have provided consent for wider sharing will be made publicly available in Zenodo.

Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?

All data made publicly available as well as results, pre-prints, papers etc. will be identified by a persistent identifier.

Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.

We will create rich metadata to allow discovery of the data. At a minimum, we plan to include the following in the metadata: dataset name, DOI, dataset description, data utility, type, keywords for search/discovery, scale, origin, license, version number, personal data/anonymized data, standards used, data sharing policy, achieving and preservation, project name, grant agreement number.

The ultimate selection of repositories (as described below in Section 4.2) will determine the metadata requirements for each dataset. We will work with the chosen repositories to develop the appropriate standard.

The interdisciplinary nature of BIAS means that there is not a single standard for metadata. We will consult the DataCite Metadata Schema for what makes the most sense for our research data.⁵

Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?

Yes

Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

Yes

4.2 Making data accessible

Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?

⁵ DataCite Metadata Working Group. (2021). DataCite Metadata Schema Documentation for the Publication and Citation of Research Data and Other Research Outputs. Version 4.4. DataCite e.V. <https://doi.org/10.14454/3w3z-sa82>

All openly available data will be deposited in a trusted repository that will assign the data an identifier resolved into a digital object.

The BIAS project has created a Community on Zenodo,⁶ where all scientific publications and most datasets will be uploaded. Zenodo's metadata standards⁷ adhere to FAIR principles, and will be adapted individually to each dataset based on the interdisciplinary nature of BIAS. BIAS has also established a public Github repository.⁸ We will also partner with the AI on Demand Platform⁹ to communicate BIAS results. Below we provide details regarding specific datasets.

DS 2.1 Survey of workers: Survey responses

This data will be uploaded to Zenodo accompanied by comprehensive metadata. This will include detailed survey documentation outlining the data collection process, in accordance with Deliverables 2.1 and 2.3. Additionally, ULEID will ensure that all variables are clearly explained, including their definitions and coding schemes. This approach guarantees that the data will be accessible, well-contextualised, and suitable for further analysis, while maintaining participant confidentiality and privacy. The upload will take place following the approval of Deliverable 2.3, which includes the final data analysis.

DS 2.2: Expert interviews: Interview responses to pre-defined questions

This will also be uploaded to Zenodo, following the same metadata standards of DS2.1

DS 2.6: Co-creation workshops: Words and phrases that indicate bias

The wordlists derived from the stakeholder activities, including the co-creation workshops are released among with the code in a public Github repository¹⁰ using an Apache License.¹¹ An initial commit is already in the Github repository and others will be added as soon as corresponding papers are published. There is also a technical report published on Arxiv with regard to the code.¹² The wordlists will be documented in corresponding scientific papers. We are additionally considering releasing the dataset on HuggingFace,¹³ another well-known repository for open models and datasets.

DS 3.5: Anonymously collected, donated cover letters/CVs

DS3.5 will be released on Zenodo.

DS 4.2: Ethnographic interviews: Anonymized verbatim transcripts in original language and English translation

During the application phase, we anticipated that DS 4.2 would be made freely available to researchers. Originally, the project opted for putting this data available for future research, but assessing the data after completion makes this not recommended.

The value of qualitative data is that it is highly specific, especially concerning case studies with interviews and observations of particular organizations with few employees, working in a highly specialized field. This makes inference to the individual and company studied highly likely, as Saunders et al write "Anonymizing qualitative research data can be challenging, especially in highly sensitive contexts."¹⁴ For people's employment, which is a sensitive situation where anonymization is key – data availability beyond the

⁶ <https://zenodo.org/communities/biasproject/>

⁷ <https://about.zenodo.org/principles/>

⁸ <https://github.com/BFH-AMI/BIAS>

⁹ <https://www.ai4europe.eu>

¹⁰ <https://github.com/BFH-AMI/BIAS>

¹¹ <https://github.com/BFH-AMI/BIAS/blob/main/LICENSE>

¹² <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2407.18689>

¹³ <https://huggingface.co/>

¹⁴ Saunders, B., Kitzinger, J., & Kitzinger, C. (2015). Anonymising interview data: Challenges and compromise in practice. *Qualitative research*, 15(5), 616-632.

original data gathering organization is not seen from the BIAS project as ethically advisable.

In their paper titled “Are we ready to share qualitative research data?”¹⁵ Mozersky et al conclude that the scientific community dealing with qualitative data sets: “Ethical and productive QDS will require overcoming barriers, creating standards, and changing long held practices among all stakeholder groups.” There has also been increasing worry in the scientific community about re-identification risks in qualitative data sets, where the detailed data from informants can be used to re-identify who they are, despite high levels of anonymization has been taken. See e.g. Henriksen-Bulmer & Jeary (2016),¹⁶ Zahra et al (2023),¹⁷ de Kok et al (2023),¹⁸ and Pascale et al (2022).¹⁹ This discussion has been evolving in the scholarly community since the BIAS proposal was originally written in 2021, with the danger of reidentification becoming especially prominent in the most recent literature. With AI tools becoming increasingly advanced and good at pattern recognition, we see it as feasible that new AI tools can be developed with capabilities to re-identify older data sets within the next decade, which would pose a huge risk for the individual informants of which data we need to protect.

Therefore, BIAS decided to change plans for qualitative data sharing from open to closed, and rather follow standard qualitative data practices of collaborating with researchers who are interested in data sets, but not by giving access to the data gathered. This is in line with current standards of qualitative data collection on high-risk data such as employment and is in line with data anonymization agreements with informants of the project.

If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

At present we plan to release data in conjunction with publications. At the conclusion of the project, the partners will determine the best way to make available any data outlined above that has not been released in conjunction with publications available. Plans for releasing data in conjunction with or independently of publications will be detailed in future updates of this Data Management Plan. At present we do not think there will need to be an embargo of research data for the purposes of patenting.

Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?

All data made accessible will be available through the standard protocol of the chosen repositories. All data will be made available with a Creative Commons or Apache 2.0 license.

If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?

¹⁵ Mozersky, J., Walsh, H., Parsons, M., McIntosh, T., Baldwin, K., & DuBois, J. M. (2020). Are we ready to share qualitative research data? Knowledge and preparedness among qualitative researchers, IRB members, and data repository curators. *IASSIST quarterly*, 43(4).

¹⁶ Henriksen-Bulmer, J., & Jeary, S. (2016). Re-identification attacks—A systematic literature review. *International Journal of Information Management*, 36(6), 1184-1192.

¹⁷ Zahra, A., Perwaiz, N., Shahzad, M., & Fraz, M. M. (2023). Person re-identification: A retrospective on domain specific open challenges and future trends. *Pattern Recognition*, 142, 109669.

¹⁸ de Kok, J. W., de la Hoz, M. Á. A., de Jong, Y., Brokke, V., Elbers, P. W., Thorat, P., ... & Borrat, X. (2023). A guide to sharing open healthcare data under the General Data Protection Regulation. *Scientific data*, 10(1), 404.

¹⁹ Pascale, J., Lineback, J. F., Bates, N., & Beatty, P. (2022). Protecting the identity of participants in qualitative research. *Journal of Survey Statistics and Methodology*, 10(3), 549-567.

At present we do not anticipate that any data we make available to other researchers will need to be restricted.

How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?

At present we do not believe this is relevant.

Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

As above, at present we do not think this is relevant.

Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement?

Yes

How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?

At present we do not see a need to remove the data from the repository, and we will deposit data in a repository that guarantees long term storage. Therefore the second question is not applicable.

Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Software will be documented with README files for each component, describing the structure of the repository and the different subcomponents, as well as how to use the software component (requirements of libraries, which commands to execute, system requirements such as operating system, etc.). The format and unities of the datasets, if applicable, will be described in the metadata. In the metadata, also a description of how the data was generated and processed will be contained.

4.3 Making data interoperable

What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?

We will use used data formats such as comma-separated values or .txt documents that we expect different communities to be able to process.

In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?

At present we do not believe this will be applicable

Will your data include qualified references²⁰ to other data (e.g. other data from your

²⁰ A qualified reference is a cross-reference that explains its intent. For example, X is regulator of Y is a much more qualified reference than X is associated with Y, or X see also Y. The goal therefore is to create as many meaningful links as possible between (meta)data resources to enrich the contextual knowledge

project, or datasets from previous research)?

At present we do not believe this will be applicable

4.4 Increasing data re-use

How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?

As mentioned above, software will be documented with README files for each component and a description of how the data was generated and processed will be contained in the metadata. The interview guide used to conduct ethnographic interviews will be provided with interview data. Information on the co-creation methodology used to generate the bias wordlists will also be included.

Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?

For data to be made freely available (DS 2.1, DS 2.2, DS 2.6, DS 3.5) will be made available in the public domain under a Creative Commons or Apache 2.0 License.

Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes, data will be placed in repositories and usable by third parties

Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?

Specific standards do not yet exist for such interdisciplinary work, especially for qualitative interview data. As stated above, such information will be made available in metadata and readme files.

Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.

5. Other research outputs

In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.)

Bias detection and mitigation modules for word embeddings and language models developed during WP3 will be publicly released through BIAS' GitHub repository²¹ or another suitable platform to release software. Details on the provision of Open-Source software have already been detailed in BIAS Deliverables "D6.3 Plans for provision for open source software" due October 31 2024 (M24), and final plans will be described in "D6.7 Final report on provision of open-source software" due October 31 2026 (M48)

about the data. (Source: <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/i3-metadata-include-qualified-references-metadata/>)

²¹ <https://github.com/BFH-AMI/BIAS>

The MOOC developed in WP5 will be hosted and freely available on Digiotech's platform to allow for longevity following the conclusion of the project. The MOOC will also be promoted on the AI on Demand Platform.

All research results will be made open access through deposition in an identified repository. Additionally, we will target publishing in fully open access journals when possible.

6. Allocation of resources

What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)? How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)

Due to the limited size of data, we expect the costs to be negligible.

We anticipate that most publications will be able to be made Open Access through the Norwegian government's agreements with scientific publishers. However, we have budgeted €30 000 for Open Access publications for any publications that cannot be made Open Access through these schemes.

Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

NTNU as Project Coordinator will be responsible for data management. The Principal Investigator and Project Administrator have and will continue to consult closely with the NTNU Research Data Office and Legal Advisors regarding data management issues. We will also work closely with the partners that generate data regarding the management of such data.

How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

We will deposit data in repositories that guarantee long term retention of data, such as Zenodo which preserves data in perpetuity. Digiotech commits to maintaining the MOOC for at-least 10 years beyond the project conclusion.

7. Data Security

What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?

This project will follow the NTNU and Norwegian standards for data security, which are generally more stringent than what would apply to other project partners.

NTNU follows the Norwegian policies for data classification and data security of research data. This categorizes data into four levels of sensitivity: Open, Internal, Confidential, and Strictly Confidential.²²

- **Open:** Information may be available to anyone without special access rights.
- **Internal:** The information must have some level of protection and may be accessible to both external and internal personnel with controlled access rights.

²² <https://www.sikresiden.no/en/preventive/securinginformation#> ; <https://i.ntnu.no/wiki/-/wiki/English/Data+storage+guide>

This category is used when there is a possibility for causing certain damage to the institution or a cooperation partner, if the information becomes known to unauthorized persons. Examples of such information may be certain work documents, information exempt from public disclosure, personal data, grades, larger student assignments, examination answer papers, research data and research work.

- **Confidential:** This category is used when there is a possibility for causing damage to the public interests, the institution, an individual or a cooperation partner, if the information becomes known to unauthorized persons. The information must thus have strict access rights. Examples of such information may be certain strategy papers, sensitive personal data, health information, examination question papers prior to the examination, certain types of research data and research work.
- **Strictly confidential:** Strictly confidential is used when there is a possibility for causing significant damage to the public interests, the institution, an individual or a cooperation partner, if the information becomes known to unauthorized persons. The information should have the highest level of access rights. Examples of such information can be large amount of health information used in research.

NTNU has different standards for secure storage and access at each classification tier.²³ All BIAS research data has been deemed to be “Internal” with the exception of DS 4.1 Ethnographic interview recordings, which are “Confidential”. Most data will be stored on an NTNU maintained Microsoft Teams site, where all project partners have password-protected access. NTNU has deemed Teams an adequate storage solution for Internal and Confidential data, provided that Confidential data is stored in an encrypted format.

Below are special procedures for datasets that differ from the general practice of storage on MS Teams:

DS 2.1 Survey of workers: Survey Responses

ULEID, the partner responsible for the survey, utilized Qualtrics²⁴—a survey platform commonly used by Leiden University—and Prolific²⁵—a commonly used platform for gathering paid survey responses. All survey data, fully anonymized at the point of collection, are securely stored on SharePoint in accordance with ULEID's internal policy. Access to this data is strictly limited to ULEID and authorized project members.

DS 3.1 Farplas application records for CBR research

This data was first acquired and curated by partner Farplas. Following curation, it was transferred to a virtual machine managed by project partner Digiotech, using their service provider GCore on nodes located in Türkiye. NTNU and BFH project members actively using the data for research purposes have access to this data, but the data never leaves Türkiye. These virtual machines have the following data security features:

- **Access control** is enabled by a combination of (i) a firewall where specific IPv4 and IPv6 addresses of the BIAS partners are whitelisted such that connections from other IP addresses are blocked and (ii) SSH public keys shared by the partners
- **Entry control** is managed by introducing a firewall where specific IPv4 and IPv6 addresses of the BIAS partners are whitelisted such that connections from other IP addresses are blocked from entering into any of the virtual machines.
- **Data sharing** is controlled through access control and authentication. Only a

²³ <https://i.ntnu.no/wiki/-/wiki/English/Data+storage+guide>

²⁴ <https://www.qualtrics.com>

²⁵ <https://www.prolific.com>

select few colleagues of FARPL, NTNU, BFH, and DIGI have access to the data sharing. Exporting any data from the virtual machines to local machines is not allowed to be inline with GDPR.

- **Transfer control** - All data is transferred using a secure encrypted channel of communication like VPN, Secure Copy (scp command of Linux).
- **Input control** - A log is kept on all three virtual machines of users who have connected to the virtual machines.
- **Order control** - The data processor (i.e., DIGI) will amend, remove or delete any data if specifically instructed by the data controller in writing (email or postal mail). Upon reception of such written instruction from the data controller, DIGI, in its data processor role, will implement a procedure to ensure compliance with any requested traceability procedure.
- **Availability control** – is governed by the following SLA agreements with cloud provider Gcore available at <https://gcore.com/legal>: Hosting SLA, Cloud SLA, DDoS protection SLA, and storage SLA. Definition of availability and how it is calculated are written in detail. Beyond that, Digiotech will implement a backup to prevent accidental data loss. One of the three virtual machines will have a designated backup of the data shared by Farplas and all processed data of NTNU, BFH, and DIGI.
- **Separation control** - In the BIAS project, data provided by FARPL is processed for the sole purpose of WP3 objectives. Therefore, separate data processing (involving storing, alterations, deletion, transmission) are not required. All (virtual machine) programming environments, data are shared with the colleagues of FARPL, NTNU, BFH, and DIGI. If any of this data is made available to other researchers, Separation Control procedures will be revisited.

DS 3.2 Farplas application records for NLP research

These procedures are the same as outlined above for DS 3.1

DS 3.4 Synthetically generated data for CBR research

These procedures are the same as outlined above for DS 3.1

DS 3.5 Anonymously collected, donated cover letters/CVs

This data will be collected by BFH using the anonymous survey platform LimeSurvey²⁶ without IP address tracking. Initial data is stored at BFH using their standard procedures for storing research data and then transferred to a VM maintained by Digiotech and provided by GCore. The data VM properties and data security are as outline above, except that this VM is located in Helsinki, Finland.

DS 4.1 Ethnographic interviews: Interview recordings

Prior to anonymization and transcription, NTNU and HI will be responsible for securing and storing interview securely in encrypted using their own institutional policies. NTNU does this through a secure Microsoft Teams site that only NTNU team members actively engaged in research will have access to. No other partner will have access to the audio recordings. Once interviews have been anonymized and transcribed, the audio recordings will be deleted, and the transcripts shared on the BIAS Microsoft Teams site.

HI recorded and transcribed interviews using the Otter app²⁷ and saved on a secure HI-only Microsoft Teams site. Only HI team members directly involved in the research and data collection have access to this site. After the interviews have been anonymized, the audio recordings will be deleted, and the transcripts will be shared on the BIAS Microsoft Teams site.

²⁶ <https://www.limesurvey.org>

²⁷ <https://otter.ai>

Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

Yes. As described above, repository selection is in process and will be determined by the next scheduled revision of this Data Management Plan.

8. Ethics

Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).

All Social Science research in Norway that involves the collection of personal data is required to be reviewed by Sikt, which evaluates whether plans for storage, sharing, and informed consent are in compliance with Norwegian law and GDPR. Such review also encompasses interview guides and questionnaires to determine if personal data is gathered during research activities. If Sikt determines that personal data is gathered, the exact wording of informed consent forms and procedures are reviewed and approved. All BIAS research activities that the research team believes may include the collection of personal data will be submitted to Sikt for approval. Below is a summary of all submissions thus far made to Sikt:

DS 2.1 Survey of workers: Survey responses

Determined to be anonymous

DS 3.1 & 3.2 Hiring records from Farplas

Approved under Public Interest (General Data Protection Regulation art. 6 nr .1 e).

Because data collection did not involve informed consent, Sikt asked that an independent ethical review of data collection procedures be undertaken at relevant institutions. NTNU does not have any ethical review committees for such research activities. The BFH Research Commission does have an Ethics Advisory Group, which approved the BIAS research plan. Additionally, Sikt required that a public notice be placed on the BIAS website concerning data subjects who may be subject to this research. This is available in English and Turkish here: <https://www.biasproject.eu/hrm-research-data/> Farplas also posted a similar notice on their website: <https://www.farplas.com/tr/inovasyon/>

Furthermore, Sikt required that we confirm that such data collection was legal under Turkish law. Farplas therefore consulted with a Turkish data protection lawyer who advised on anonymization procedures to be compliant with Turkish data protection legislation. They also recommended that data not be transferred outside Türkiye, resulting in the VMs where such data is stored being located in Türkiye.

Thus far we have submitted information about the Expert Interviews and Survey of Workers, and Sikt has determined that neither activity gathers personal data.

DS 3.5 Anonymously collected, donated cover letters/CVs

Approved under Consent (General Data Protection Regulation art. 6 nr. 1 a)

DS 4.1 Ethnographic interviews

Approved under Consent (General Data Protection Regulation art. 6 nr. 1 a). and Explicit consent (General Data Protection Regulation art. 9 nr. 2 a)

Consent forms for Turkish participants includes consent for recordings to be transferred outside Türkiye for the purposes of transcription and anonymization.

Will informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

As stated above, the following datasets are being considered for long-term preservation that may contain personal data.

DS 2.1: Survey of workers: Survey responses

Not relevant, as Sikt determined that the survey did not contain personal information

DS 3.1: Farplas application records for CBR research

Scope of long-term preservation not yet determined. If the decision is made to store data long term or make it available to other researchers, additional approval from Sikt will be sought. Because of the nature of the data, informed consent will not be possible.

DS 3.2: Farplas application records for NLP research

The same situation as for DS 3.1

DS 3.5: Anonymously collected, donated cover letters/CVs

Consent form has an ability to consent either for long term preservation and sharing outside the consortium or only sharing data within the context of BIAS project. Only data coming from data subjects that consent for sharing data outside the consortium will be kept for long-term preservation.

DS 4.2: Ethnographic interviews: Anonymized verbatim transcripts in original language and English translation

Consent did not specify what would happen with anonymized interview transcripts. Long-term preservation will be determined in consultation of Sikt.

What are the mechanisms for transfer of data and access requests between EU and non-EU countries beyond sharing of data internally in the consortium for research purposes?

At present, we do not anticipate any transfer of personal data from EU member states to non-member states except for research data transferred among the consortium members.

DS 2.1 Survey of workers: Survey responses; DS 2.2 Expert interviews: Interview responses to pre-defined questions; DS 2.6 Co-creation activities: Words and phrases that indicate bias do not contain personal data.

As outlined above, donated cover letters collected in DS3.5 from volunteers who have given their consent for sharing their data outside the consortium will be made available on Zenodo. Because of this consent, no special procedures will be needed.

9. Other Issues

Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?

Advice has been sought from the NTNU Research Data Office and Legal Advisors, as well as SIKT, regarding BIAS research data. This has included advice regarding legal agreements between partners that need to be in place regarding various data. Following these discussions, they have determined that the following agreements are necessary in relation to DS 3.1 & DS 3.2, which have been signed and entered into force:

- Data transfer agreement between FARPL and NTNU/BFH
- Joint controllership agreement between NTNU and BFH
- Joint data processing agreement between NTNU/BFH and Digiotech

- Data processing agreement between Digiotech and GCore

Additionally, research conducted by the University of Iceland was submitted to and approved by the Research Ethics Committee of Public Higher Education Institutions in Iceland.

Stakeholder feedback

The BIAS project values feedback from stakeholders including researchers, participants, and the general public to improve data management practices. All BIAS Data Management Plans are public deliverables and, once approved, are available on the BIAS website at <https://www.biasproject.eu/public-reports/>. We will publicize this publication and offer a mechanism for any stakeholder to comment by emailing info@biasproject.eu. Additionally, following best practices outlined in the Horizon Europe Programme Guide,²⁸ approved Data Management Plans will be made available at DMPOnline.²⁹

Furthermore, we will incorporate discussion of data management practices into project activities with stakeholders that we believe would have a vested interest in data management practices and when project activities are of a sufficient duration to accommodate such a discussion. Currently we plan to include such a discussion in the BIAS Spring School on Trustworthy and Fair AI to be hosted by partner Digiotech in Tallinn, Estonia in April 2025.

²⁸ https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/programme-guide_horizon_en.pdf

²⁹ <https://dmponline.dcc.ac.uk>

BIAS

Mitigating biases
of AI in the
labour market

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email
info@biasproject.eu

website
www.biasproject.eu

social media
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